

New Route for the Preparation of 2H-3-Aryl-3,4-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines and 2H-3-Aryl-3,4-dihydro-4-methyl-1,3-benzoxazines

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2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (1) and 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethanone (2) on reaction with different primary aromatic amines gave 2-(arylimino)methylphenols (3) and 2-[1-(arylimino)ethyl]phenols (4), respectively. 3 and 4 on reduction with sodium borohydride gave 2-(arylamino)methylphenols (5) and 2-[1-(arylamino)ethyl]phenols (6), which underwent cyclisation with formaldehyde to form 2H-3-aryl-3,4-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines (7) and 2H-3-aryl-3,4-dihydro-4-methyl-1,3-benzoxazines (8), respectively.

DIVERSE activities have been reported to be associated with 3-aryl/alkyl-2H-3,4-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines¹⁻⁵. They are also used in the preparation of polymers⁶. These compounds can be prepared in one-step by the Mannich reaction of a primary amine with the appropriate phenol in presence of an excess of formaldehyde. However, the yields in this method are somewhat less. Besides, some other methods for the preparation of these compounds are reported^{7,8}.

Realising the importance of 1,3-benzoxazines during our investigations on internal Mannich reactions, we tried to develop a new route for the synthesis of these compounds (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (1) and 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethanone (2) were condensed with different primary aromatic amines to obtain 2-(arylimino)methylphenols (3) and 2-[1-(arylimino)ethyl]phenols (4), respectively. 3 and 4 were subsequently reduced by NaBH₄ in methanol to 2-(arylamino)methylphenols (5) and 2-[1-(arylamino)ethyl]phenols (6),

respectively. The reaction of formaldehyde on 5 and 6 gave 2H-3-aryl-3,4-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines (7) and 2H-3-aryl-3,4-dihydro-4-methyl-1,3-benzoxazines (8), respectively, through internal Mannich reaction.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries on a Campbell apparatus and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Bruker 80 MHz instrument. Elemental analyses were found satisfactory for the compounds. Physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
3a	H	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO	55-6	96
3b	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂	84-5	94
3c	H	CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO	88-9	96
3d	H	Cl	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClNO	88-9	94
3e	H	NO ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	134-35	89
4a	CH ₃	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO	81-2	91
4b	CH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO ₂	98-9	87
4c	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO	40-1	87
5a	H	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO	116-17	95
5b	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂	133-34	94
5c	H	CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO	109-10	95
5d	H	Cl	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClNO	114-15	95
5e	H	NO ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	123-24	90
6a	OH ₂	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO	60-1	91
6b	OH ₂	OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO ₂	121-22	92
6c	OH ₂	OH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO	86-7	91
7a	H	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO	56-7	94
7b	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO ₂	78-9	95
7c	H	CH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO	71-2	94
7d	H	Cl	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClNO	51-2	91
7e	H	NO ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	103-04	89
8a	OH ₂	H	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO	Gum	89
8b	OH ₂	OCH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NO ₂	Gum	91
8c	OH ₂	CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NO	Gum	92

2-(Arylimino)methylphenols (3a-e) : Salicylaldehyde (1; 2.44 g, 0.002 mol) and appropriate aniline (0.002 mol) were refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) for 30 min. Crystalline residue, deposited on cooling, was further purified by crystallisation from chloroform-petrol (2 : 8, v/v) to afford 3a-e.

2-[1-(Arylimino)ethyl]phenols (4a-c) : 1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)ethanone (2; 2.72 g, 0.002 mol) and appropriate aniline (0.002 mol) were refluxed in dry xylene (10 ml) for 6 h. Xylene was removed under reduced pressure and petrol added to the residue. Crystals, separated on cooling, were recrystallised from chloroform-petrol (2 : 8, v/v) to afford 4a-c.

2-(Arylamino)methylphenol (5a-e) : NaBH₄ (0.3 g) was added to a solution of 2-(arylimino)-methylphenol (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) and the mixture stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The residue, separated on pouring the solution into cold water, was further crystallised from ethanol to furnish 5a-e : 5b, ν_{\max} 3 260 (NH) and 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ (CDCl₃) 3.65 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 4.25 (2H, s, ArCH₂N) and 6.6-7.2 (10H, m, Ar-H, -OH and -NH). Compounds 6a-c were prepared from 2-[1-(arylimino)ethyl]phenols (4a-c) by the same method.

2H-3-Aryl-3,4-dihydro-1,3-benzoxazines (7a-c) : 2-(Arylamino)methylphenols (0.005 mol) and for-

malin (37%, 1 ml) were refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) for 5 h. The residue, obtained after pouring the reaction mixture into cold water, was crystallised from ethanol to give 7a-e : 7a, ν_{\max} 1 600, 1 580, 1 490, 1 360, 1 220 and 750 cm⁻¹; 7b, δ (CDCl₃) 3.75 (3H, s, ArOCH₃), 4.55 (2H, s, ArCH₂N), 5.30 (2H, s, OCH₂N) and 6.8-7.2 (8H, m, ArH). Compounds 8a-c were prepared from 6a-c by the same method. 8a, δ (CDCl₃) 1.75 (3H, d, CH₃, *J* 7 Hz), 4.75 (1H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CHCH₃), 5.30 (1H, d, *J*_{gem} 12 Hz, O-CH₂H_b), 5.5 (1H, d, *J*_{gem} 12 Hz, OCH₂H_b), 6.8-7.5 (9H, m, ArH).

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